

DJANGO FRAMEWORK PLATFORMASI VA UNING IMKONIYATLARI.

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Dasturlash kasbining hozirgi zamondagi ahamiyati qanchalik yuqoriligi endi hech kimga yangilik emas. Ayniqsa web dasturchilarga talab yuqorilab bormoqda. Sababi juda ko'plab yangi biznes sektorlar, startaplar, tashkilotlar, korxonalar o'z ish faoliyatlarini boshlab yuqori bosqichga olib chiqishmoqda. Bunda ularning ishini qulaylashtirish, yangi bosqichga olib chiqishda web ilovalarning o'rnini beqiyos. Hozirgi web dasturlash sanoatida Django frameworkning mashhurligi tobora ortib bormoqda. Ko'pgina kompaniyalar va dasturchilar uchun hamda alohida loyihalarni amalga oshirish uchun Django framework chindan eng yaxshi tanlov bo'lib qolmoqda.

Django murakkab parametrlarga ega filtirlash tizimlarini yaratish uchun, mashinani o'rganish, ma'lumotlarni tahlil qilish uchun mo'ljallangan. Django da web-saytlarni ishlab chiqish har qanday murakkablikdagi loyihani amalga oshirishga imkon beradi. Django web-saytni yaratish - bu ishlab chiquvchi uchun yoqimli jarayon. Platforma iloji boricha qulay va tushunarli, xatolarni osongina aniqlash yoki murakkab muammolarni o'z vaqtida hal qilishga yordam beradi. Shu jumladan quyidagi afzalliklarga ega:

Django platformasining imkoniyatlari keng:

ko'plab tillarni qo'llab-quvvatlaydigan sayt ma'muriy panelining tayyor interfeysi;
dastur arxitekturasiga ulanish oson, shuning uchun uni istalgan Django saytlariga o'rnatish mumkin;

tayyor keshlash tizimi;

qulay filtr tizimi;

o'rnatilgan hujjatlar;

Django da web-saytlarni ishlab chiqish ko'plab muammolarni hal qilishga imkon beradi. Uning imkoniyatlari va vazifalari juda ko'p. Django quyidagi vazifalarni bajaradi:

platformada kuchli funksional imkoniyatlarga ega bo'lgan to'liq huquqli CRM tizimi ishlab chiqishi mumkin;

Django web-resurs uchun kerakli imkoniyatlarga ega bo'lgan CMS yaratish uchun juda qulay;

Aloqa platformalari yaratish uchun mo'ljallangan;

Siz Django da xonani bronlashtirish xizmatini yaratishingiz mumkin;

Hujjatlarni boshqarish platformasini yaratish uchun foydalaniladi;

Django frameworki qo'llanilishi:

Django-python dasturlash tilida web ilovalar ishlab chiqish uchun ajoyib frameworkdir. Framework python dasturlash tilida yozilgan. Django frameworki birinchi bor 2005-yil 21-iyulda ishga tushirilgan va bosqichma bosqich eng yaxshi frameworklar qatoridan o'rin egalladi. Ushbu framework krossplatformalikdir (ya'ni barcha operatsion tizimlarni qo'llab-quvvatlaydi). Django da yaratilgan sayt bir yoki bir nechta ilovalardan tashkil topishi mumkin. Ushbu frameworkning ishlab prinsiplaridan biri bu-DRY (Don't repeat yourself - o'z-o'zingni takrorlama) ya'ni bir kodni qaytadan yozishga hojat yo'q, bu esa web ilovani yaratilish protsessini tezlashtiradi. Bu framework MCV loyihalashtirish shablonidan foydalanadi.

Django ning texnik xususiyatlari quyidagilardan iborat:

Sodda sintaks

O'z shaxsiy server

MVC (Model-View-Controller)

“Batteries included” ya’ni oddiy masalalarni hal qilish uchun zarur bo’lgan barcha narsalar o’zi bilan birga kelishi

ORM(Object Relational Mapper) ya’ni obyekt bilan bog’liqlik xaritasi

HTTP kutubxonlari

Middlewareni qo’llab-quvvatlash

Python blokining test framework

Nega web dasturlashda foydalanishimiz kerak?

Tez va oson: Djangoing asosiy maqsadlarida biri dasturchilar uchun oson va tez ishlashni ta’minlash;

Xavfsiz: Xavfsizlik Djangoing yuqori ustuvorlik tomoni hisoblanadi.U eng yaxshi tashqi xavfsizlik tizimlaridan biriga ega va dasturchilarga umumiy xavfsizlik muammolaridan xalos bo’lishga yordam beradi;

Har qanday web dastur loyihasiga mos tushadi:Django yordamida oddiy web saytlardan tortib kata yuklamali web-ilovalargacha bo’lgan har qanday kattalikdagi va hajmdagi loyihalarni muvafaqiyatli bajarish mumkin;

Kuchli ishlab chiqilgan: Django-open-source frameworklarining eng kuchli dokumentatsiyalari asosida ishlab chiqilgan.Hamda hozirda ham yuqori darajada ushlab turilibdi.Yangi funksiyalar va tuzatishlar billan birga doimiy yangilanib boradi.

Django framework bilan nimalar qila olishimiz mumnik?

eng ajoyib va murakkab funksiyali web ilovalar

istalgan murakablikdagi dinamik web saytlar

elektron tijorat web-saytlari

sog’liqni saqlashga va shifoxonalarga oid web ilovalar

Transport harakatlari uchun va buyumlari uchun moliyaviy ilovalar va boshqalar

Djangodan shuningdek, alohida vazifalarni bajaradigan kichik tizimlarni ham ishlab chiqish mumkin,masalan:

Foydalanuvchilarga bildirishnomalarni yuborish uchun electron pochta tizimi

Algoritmgga asoslangan generatorlar

Ma’lunotlarni tahlil qilish vositalari

Administrator boshqaruv panellari

Fotosuratga asoslangan tekshirish va parol tizimlari

Investitsion fondlarni tahlil qilish vositalari

Django frameworkidan foydalanadigan mashhur kompaniyalar

Instagram: Media ma’lumotlari va foydalanuvchilarning o’zaro aloqalari bilan shug’ullanadigan yana bir ijtimoiy tarmoq.

Spofitify: Foydalanuvchilarga musiqani bepul yoki reklamasiz obuna asosida tinglash imkonini beradigan juda katta miqdordagi ma’lumotlarga ega bo’lgan yirik media kutubxonasi.

Mozilla: Eng mashhur web-brauzerlardan biri va PHP dan Pythonga Django sababli o’tgan yana bir web-dastur.

NASA: Ular Djangodan eng ishonchlilikni talab qiladigan ba'zi funksional elementlari uchun foydalaniladi.

Dropbox: Ma'lumotlarni saqlash uchun bulutli texnologiyalar yuqori samaradorlikni talab qiladi.

Ishlab chiqaruvchilar Django saytini qurish oddiy va samarali ekanligiga ishonishadi. Ammo eng muhimi shundaki, sayt kuchli va funksional bo'lib chiqadi. Keyin web-resurs uchun qobiq yaratadigan va uni rivojlanishning so'nggi bosqichiga olib boradigan dizaynerlar.

Xulosa: Djangoda web-saytlarni ishlab chiqarish dolzarb bo'lib hisoblanadi. Platforma sizga kodni tezda tushunishga, kutubxonalardan tayyor yechimlardan foydalanishga va rivojlanish jarayonini sezilarli darajada tezlashtirishga imkon beradi. Albatta, kichik onlayn-do'konlarda va kichik loyihalarda Django saytini ishlab chiqishdan foydalanish dolzarb emas, loyigani amalga oshirishning usullari juda oson. Ammo kata resurslar uchun juda yaxshi va foydalidir.

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